

Deliverable 1.2

DMP & Policies

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1.0	Salomé Landel (CNRS)	Final version

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC 0	Creative Commons Zero
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution licence
CC BY-NC	Creative Commons NonCommercial license
CC BY-ND	Creative Commons Attribution NoDerivs
CERN	Conseil européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EUDAT	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
Gdrive	Google Drive
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language
INRIA	Institut National de Recherche Informatique et Automatique

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IPR	Intellectual Property Right
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
ODbL	Open Database License
ORCID	Open Researcher & Contributor IDentification
PCO	Project Coordination Office
PID	Persistent Identifier
SSO	Single Sign-On
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
US	United States
WP	Work Package
WML	eXtensible Markup Language

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Executive summary

The LUMEN project is organised in 8 WPs, involving 20 organisations from 10 countries and about 90 individuals. Positioned at the interface between research and engineering, the project aims to develop a white-label discovery platform that adapts to the diverse needs of scientific communities by providing a user-friendly tool for data sharing.

This DMP is designed to manage the data associated with the development and deployment of the LUMEN components: white-label discovery platform, meta-search engine, infrastructure for semantics, etc. This DMP identifies all types of data that will be generated or reused during the three-year project, and outlines measures to ensure that the data is FAIR and compliant with GDPR requirements.

This DMP excludes data from the scientific communities involved in LUMEN (Mathematics, Social Sciences and Humanities, Molecular Dynamics, Earth System Science). The project is not responsible for managing their data, but only for developing tools to facilitate its sharing.

The DMP follows the Horizon Europe guidelines for DMPs. It is based on thorough desk research and input from data management experts, LUMEN WP Leaders and the LUMEN Technical Coordinator. This document is designed to be dynamic, evolving as new research data are integrated into the project.

The main benefits of this DMP are to serve as a guide for project members, ensure the reproducibility of LUMEN's development, and enhance the long-term sustainability of the platform by maintaining clear records of data origins and evolution. This DMP also aims to ensure that all LUMEN data is GDPR compliant, thereby protecting personal information.

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Introduction

This deliverable has been produced as part of the LUMEN project, specifically within WP1 (Management, Coordination and Synchronisation).

The overall objective of LUMEN is to enhance cross-disciplinary collaboration by improving two existing platforms and developing two new ones through the creation of a White-Label system. All four platforms will be integrated into a federated and interoperable data mesh architecture, enabling researchers from different disciplines to seamlessly access, share and enrich research data. By bringing together domain-specific communities and technical partners, LUMEN aims to create a sustainable and scalable ecosystem that promotes interoperability, openness and cross-domain knowledge sharing.

The purpose of this DMP is to identify LUMEN research data and outline how they will be managed during the LUMEN project.

The scope of this DMP is limited to the data generated and reused for the development of LUMEN components. It excludes data from the scientific communities involved in LUMEN. The project is not responsible for managing community data, but only for developing tools to facilitate the sharing of these data. This distinction reflects the broader architectural approach adopted by LUMEN, which promotes a federated data mesh model while keeping the governance of community-managed data outside the scope of this plan.

One of the objectives of the project is to ensure that the tools and resources used to implement the platforms remain accessible after the end of the project, thereby facilitating the reproducibility of the work carried out during the three years of the LUMEN project. The DMP is an opportunity in this context, as FAIR data contribute to the reproducibility of the research.

In order to clarify how data will be managed in the LUMEN project, this document is divided into six main sections, largely based on the European Commission's template for Horizon Europe projects.

The appendices provide practical tools for project members to ensure that the DMP policies are accessible to all stakeholders.

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1. LUMEN Data scope

1.1 Definitions

Research data is defined as the evidence used to inform or support research conclusions. According to the EOSC Glossary, it includes data collected or generated during scientific research that is used as evidence in the research process or is recognised by the research community as necessary to validate findings¹.

Examples of research data: documents, spreadsheets, laboratory notebooks, field notes, diaries, questionnaires, transcripts, codebooks, audio recordings and database content².

Research software: source code, files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows, and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose³.

Software components (e.g., operating systems, libraries, dependencies, packages, scripts, etc.) that are used for research but were not created during or with a clear research intent should be considered software in research and not Research Software⁴.

1.2 LUMEN Internal / external scope

Over the course of the three-year LUMEN project, two parallel streams of research data will be managed:

- LUMEN will generate research data to understand user needs, assess business opportunities, support platform development, etc. This will include a variety of outputs from the project's WPs.
- Four scientific communities - Mathematics, Social Sciences and Humanities, Earth System Science and Molecular Dynamics - will produce and manipulate research data as part of their own disciplinary activities.

The LUMEN project aims to facilitate access to the data produced by these scientific communities. Some of these communities have already established infrastructures

¹ DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/1024 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), modified -- reference to data. Sources: https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/EOSCPartnershipMF_Glossary.pdf

² Graber-Soudry, Ohad & Minssen, Timo & Nilsson, Daniel & Wested, Jakob & Corrales Compagnucci, Marcelo & Illien, Benedicte. (2021). Legal Interoperability and the FAIR Data Principles: An X-officio study commissioned by the EOSC FAIR Working Group. 10.5281/zenodo.4471312. P.13

³ Gruenpeter, M. et al., 2021. Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504016>

⁴ EOSC Association. (2025). EOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577> - P.34

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to support data sharing and harmonisation, such as the Centre Mersenne for mathematics, OPERAS for the social sciences and humanities, and Data Terra for the Earth system domain.

In the context of this DMP, only research data directly created or reused by the LUMEN WPs will be characterised. **While the project may influence community data practices in the medium to long term - notably by proposing standards - the scientific communities themselves remain the primary stakeholders responsible for their own research data. The LUMEN project does not manage these data and its WPs do not take responsibility for them.** This distinction is illustrated in Figure 1 (see below).

Figure 1 - Representation of LUMEN data perimeter

This DMP therefore focuses exclusively on data generated and reused internally by the LUMEN project during its three year duration. It covers data produced and reused by WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8.

1.3 LUMEN Data summary

A clear distinction is made between operational data and research data. Both types are generated during the project, but each serves a different purpose:

- **Operational data:** includes data used to run the project, such as compiling event attendance, sending newsletters and other administrative functions. While operational data is designed to be GDPR compliant, it is not necessarily required to adhere to the FAIR principles, as its use is for specific purposes and timeframes rather than scientific innovation.
- **Research data:** underpins the development of the platforms and contributes to the creation of interoperable solutions for sharing scientific knowledge at EOSC level. As this data is part of the process of designing, testing, improving

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and implementing innovative tools, it must be compliant with both FAIR and GDPR.

1.3.1 LUMEN Operational data

The project will collect, analyse, store and publish different types of **operational data** through the following activities:

- **Video recordings** of platform usage and promotional videos will be produced to document and showcase the progress of the project.
- **Newsletters:** collection of email addresses and generation of newsletters.
- **Podcasts** will be developed and made public along the project to disseminate LUMEN and EOSC associated developments.
- **Periodic reportings:** a technical and financial report will be prepared every 6 months during the project. The aim is to monitor project developments.
- **Management tools** will be developed to monitor the project.
- **Indexes:** data is stored in Elasticsearch indexes. This will include both reused content (for the existing GoTriple data) and new content created for GoTriple and the Discovery Platforms.

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
Management tools	Excel; Word; PDF	Project Gdrive	Consent through registration	Restricted: project perimeter	All WPs	Management tools will be developed to monitor the project. They will remain internal.
Periodic reportings	Word; PDF; Excel	Project Gdrive	None	Restricted: project perimeter	WP1	A technical and financial report will be prepared every 6 months during the project. The aim is to monitor project developments. It will remain for internal use.
Video recordings	MP4; CSV	Project Gdrive; UNIZD Onedrive	Author information (name, affiliation); consent through registration	Public	WP3	Communication campaigns
Index	Data stored in Elasticsearch indexes (partially reused, for the present GoTriple data; created for all new content, both for	Elasticsearch server installed at PSNC server farm	Available to data processors only; consent through registration form	Restricted: project perimeter	WP4	This concerns the actual data that the Discovery Platforms make available to users. We have also included user registration data in this point: users will only be able to register on the Discovery Platforms if they explicitly accept certain conditions.

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
	GoTriple and the Discovery Platforms)					
Video recordings	MP4	Project Gdrive & website; Zenodo; Youtube	Anonymisation before publication	Public	WP8	User evaluation of the platform
Newsletter	Excel; CSV	Project Gdrive; Mailchimp	Consent through registration	Restricted: project perimeter	WP8	A newsletter will be created for the implementation of the communication & dissemination strategy. Email addresses for the newsletter subscription are collected via self-registration (Mailchimp).
Podcast	MP3; txt (transcript on website)	Acast hosting platform	Interview content	Public	WP8	As part of effective community engagement efforts (T8.5), a podcast will be produced and made publicly available.

Table 1 - List of operational data to be generated by LUMEN

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1.3.2 LUMEN Research data

The project will collect, analyse, store and publish different types of **research data** through the following activities:

- **Catalogues:** two catalogues will be created containing information on data products and software cited in scientific publications. These catalogues will include links to the relevant publications and provide a single point of access to distributed information.
- **Code⁵:** software and programming code will be developed to implement the White-label discovery platforms, the LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics and innovative tools. These will include a meta-search service, a chatbot, visualisation tools, a software catalogue and others. This development will include integration mechanisms for the hosting platforms (e.g. deployment scripts, GitLab pipelines, Jenkins jobs) and the creation of APIs for external data sharing. Some existing code will also be modified or extended to enhance existing platforms.
- **Interviews** will be conducted by WP2 and WP3 to respectively document the insights of ontology experts and to address user needs during the preparation and testing phases.
- **Workshops output:** co-design workshops will be organised to involve potential users in the platform design process. Internal workshops will focus on competitor and market analysis.
- **Eye tracking data:** visual data will be generated that captures users' eye movements as they interact with the platforms. This data will support the team's development efforts by informing interface improvements.
- **Deliverables:** over three years, 32 deliverables are expected to document the progress of the project.
- **Statistics:** to support future content analysis of the platform - covering aspects such as authorship, publication trends, potential re-use, OPERAS metrics, open citations and site statistics (including user demographics and geolocation) - relevant statistical data will be collected.
- **Surveys** will be implemented in WP3, WP6 and WP8 to gain further insights.

⁵ The decision has been made to include software under the code category, as the basic data for software is code. This decision has been made in accordance with the LUMEN technical coordinator.

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
Deliverables	PDF	Project Gdrive (not publicly accessible) ; Zenodo	Yes	Public after anonymisation	All WPs	32 deliverables are expected in the LUMEN project
Code	Software code in different programming languages and managed in OPERAS' GitLab repository	GitLab; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Restricted: project perimeter	WP2	This involves developing the software code needed to implement the FAIR Semantic Management Space.
Interviews	MP4; PDF	B2Share	Authorship of developers; Nationality; Ontology experience	Public after anonymisation	WP2	In order to identify the needs for the platform, interviews will be conducted with ontology experts.
Interviews	MP3 audio; docx; txt files	B2Share; Abertay research Drive (not publicly accessible)	Yes	Public after anonymisation	WP3	User interviews to identify the needs of researchers in the context of LUMEN and evaluate uses of the platforms
Workshops output	MP4; docx & txt files; miro boards; interface sketches as .png	B2Share; Abertay research Drive (not publicly accessible)	Yes	Public after anonymisation	WP3	Codesign sessions with users

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
Surveys	CSV	B2Share; Abertay Research Drive (not publicly accessible)	Yes	Public after anonymisation	WP3	Currently planned beyond GA to grasp better the different domains, sampling will be done using publications and the questionnaire will be distributed using Qualtrics
Surveys	MP4; CSV	Project Gdrive; UNIZD OneDrive (not publicly accessible)	Yes	Restricted: project perimeter	WP3	User evaluation of the interface design
Eye tracking data	MP4; CSV; images (heat maps)	Project Gdrive; UNIZD OneDrive (not publicly accessible)	Yes, informed consent to be signed	Restricted: project perimeter	WP3; WP6	Evaluation of the use of the platform
Catalogue	YAML; CSV; HTML; JSON-LD	GitLab	No personal info collected	Restricted: project perimeter	WP4	The Data Product Catalogue and Data Contracts are formal artefacts produced to describe the resources federated into the LUMEN Mesh. Data Contracts are authored using Baserow and exported in ODSCS compliant YAML, while Data Products are catalogued with metadata using DCAT/SKG-IF to enable FAIR discovery and federation.
Code	Software code in different programming languages and	GitLab; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public	WP4	This involves the development of the software code required to implement the upgraded version of GoTriple.

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
	managed in OPERAS' GitLab repository					
Code	Software code in different programming languages and managed in OPERAS' GitLab repository	GitLab; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public; Open Source	WP4	This involves the development of the software code required to implement the White Label Discovery Platforms.
Code	Software code in different programming languages	GitLab; GitHub; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public; Open Source	WP4	This involves the development of the software code required to implement the advanced tools for the production of mathematical articles.
Code	.PY; BASH; .YAML; JSON	GitLab; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public	WP5	Integration mechanisms for hosting platforms (deployment scripts, pipelines in gitlab, jobs in jenkins).
Code	API documentation (API in .PY or .JAVA)	GitLab; Confluence; Swagger; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public	WP5	Implementing the code (creating an API) and sharing the results externally (via API) (related to the D5.3)
Catalogue	Codemeta	Software Heritage	Author information (name, affiliation)	Public; Open access	WP6	This dataset provides a set of information on software mentioned in scientific publications, with links to these publications. It is expected to use data developed for the

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
						French Catalogue of Academic Research Software, but may also generate new data.
Code	Software code in different programming languages	GitLab; GitHub; Software Heritage	Authorship of developers	Public	WP6	This dataset contains programming code for task-related software components in WP6, such as meta-search services, chatbots, visualisation tools, software catalogues and others.
Statistics	Txt, CSV, HTML, XML	Project website	Author information (name, affiliation)	Public through website	WP6	This dataset contains a set of statistics on authors and publications. A potential reuse of ZBMath Open, Operas Metrics and Open Citations data is envisioned, but also the creation of new metrics.
Surveys	CSV	Project Gdrive; UNIZD OneDrive (not publicly accessible), B2SHARE	Yes	Anonymisation before publication	WP6	Testing and feedback phase will be implemented to test the use cases.
Workshops output	PDF (screenshots from miro boards)	Zenodo; project Gdrive (not publicly accessible)	No personal information collected	Public	WP7	Workshops where we discuss the contextual factors around our proposed solutions, strengths, weaknesses and gaps, bringing in information from competitor analysis and user studies.
Analytical tables	Excel; CSV	Project Gdrive (not publicly accessible); Zenodo	No personal information collected	Public	WP7	Information on the main competitors / alternative solutions to the solutions developed within LUMEN.

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Data type	Data format	Retention	Personal information	Dissemination level	WP associated	Comments
Statistics	HTML; CSV	Project website; project reports	Geolocation; User stats; Consent given through banner	Public through project reports; Zenodo	WP8	Website Statistics (user stats, geolocation) are being collected for monitoring purposes; will be featured in project reports etc.
Surveys	CSV; Excel; PDF	Project Gdrive (not publicly accessible); project website; Zenodo	Yes	Anonymisation before publication	WP8	Notably to target engagement activities.

Table 2 - List of research data to be generated by LUMEN

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1.4 LUMEN Data management steps

The LUMEN data management is divided into three phases:

1. Continuous storage and backups along the project: Google Drive and GitLab.
2. Data sharing - once the final version is ready: Zenodo, B2SHARE, Software Heritage.
3. Long-term preservation: to be decided at the end of the project.

Figure 2 - LUMEN Data management steps

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2. Making data FAIR

2.1 Making data Findable

Record data in an accessible repository

All LUMEN research data will be published in relevant open repositories:

- Catalogues, anonymised interviews, eye tracking data, statistics, surveys, will be deposited on **B2SHARE**⁶;
- Workshops outputs, deliverables will be deposited on **Zenodo**⁷;
- Once finalised, the code⁸ developed in GitLab will be deposited on **Software Heritage**⁹.

Assigning a PID

Each LUMEN research data produced by the LUMEN project will be associated with a PID. This will be done when the research data is deposited on either B2SHARE, Zenodo or Software Heritage:

- Assignment of a DOI on Zenodo;
- Assignment of Handle PID or DOI on B2SHARE;
- Assignment of SWHIDs¹⁰ on Software Heritage.

This allows data to be found even if its location changes. These PIDs are stable and widely used in the EOSC and European research environment.

Associate Data with rich metadata

LUMEN research data will be associated with rich metadata. This will be done in both machine and human actionable formats. By using open repositories with standardised and compatible metadata formats, the project will ensure that the data are easily harvestable and indexable, thereby enhancing their discoverability in the wider digital ecosystem. The LUMEN teams are committed to complete as many metadata fields as possible on the repositories.

⁶ EUDAT. (n.d.) *B2SHARE – Store and Share Research Data*. Available at: <https://B2SHARE.eudat.eu/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

⁷ Zenodo. (n.d.). *Zenodo*. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/> (Accessed: 4 April 2025)

⁸ possibility to declare the LUMEN GitLab to Software Heritage to allow data migration

⁹ **Software Heritage**. (n.d.) *Software Heritage – Preserving Software, Enabling Reuse*. Available at: <https://www.softwareheritage.org/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

¹⁰ **Software Heritage**. (n.d.) *Persistent Identifiers – SWH Data Model Documentation*. Available at: <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/swh-model/persistent-identifiers.html> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

File naming

Every LUMEN data should be named following this format:
LUMEN_title_of_data_VX_YYYY_MM_DD.

Example: LUMEN_D1.2_DMPs_and_Policies_V1_2025_06_16

Internal LUMEN policy:

Deposit LUMEN research data on Zenodo, B2SHARE, or Software Heritage
Fill as much metadata fields as possible
Add keywords: LUMEN + EOSC + relevant keywords according to the content

2.2 Making data accessible

Deposit in a trusted repository:

LUMEN will deposit its data in trusted repositories managed by sustainable organisations:

- Zenodo is sponsored by CERN and funded by the European Commission. It uses standardised protocols for storage.
- B2SHARE is managed by EUDAT, an organisation with experience in supporting European research data management projects. They follow the FAIR principles and are integrated into the EOSC ecosystem.
- Software Heritage is managed by INRIA and is recognised in the EOSC landscape. They propose an infrastructure for the preservation of software code. It is the only type of research data they manage and they have developed specific tools to make the deposited data, FAIR.

Deposit for long-term preservation

At the end of the project, the Executive Board will consider long-term preservation, one option being a CoreTrust Seal¹¹ certified repository.

Licences

The licensing approach is to allow reuse, but with attribution (author, sources). The following licences are envisaged:

- **Deliverables and workshop outputs:** Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY), or a licence with equivalent rights; for

¹¹ CoreTrustSeal – Certified Trustworthy Data Repositories, [online] Available at: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/> [Accessed 16 Jun. 2025].

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monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND)¹².

- **Metadata of deposited data** must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable)¹³.
- **Catalogues, Indexes, Anonymised interviews, Eye tracking data, Statistics, Surveys:** CC BY or ODbL¹⁴ if database.
- **Code:** BSD 2-Clause¹⁵ or BSD-3 Clause¹⁶ Licence.

Sensitive information

Access to the LUMEN shared drive is restricted to project members, with access provided by the PCO. In cases where tasks involve sensitive data, such information will be stored in internal institutional repositories with restricted public access. Sharing in repositories will only be done after anonymisation.

Embargo period

No embargo period is anticipated at this stage; should one become necessary, its justification will be clearly explained and its duration kept to a minimum.

Data Access Committee

The project does not require a Data Access Committee for internally generated or re-used data, as **there is one clear rule for all: personal data shall be anonymised before sharing.**

The LUMEN project will deal with personal data. The project team does not plan to deal with other types of sensitive data such as medical, financial, banking, identification, legal, judicial, military, governmental or cybersecurity data.

Independent access to metadata

Zenodo, Software Heritage¹⁷ and B2SHARE¹⁸ ensures the separation of data and metadata, even when access to data is restricted. The metadata remains in open

¹² See appendix 5 of the GA - P.11.

¹³ See appendix 5 of the GA - P.11.

¹⁴ **Open Data Commons.** (n.d.) *Open Database Licence (ODbL) v1.0.* Available at: <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

¹⁵ **SPDX.** (n.d.) *BSD 2-Clause License.* Available at: <https://spdx.org/licenses/BSD-2-Clause.html#licenseText> (Accessed: 22 April 2025).

¹⁶ **SPDX.** (n.d.) *BSD 3-Clause License.* Available at: <https://spdx.org/licenses/BSD-3-Clause.html#licenseText> (Accessed: 22 April 2025).

¹⁷ **Software Heritage.** (n.d.) *Metadata - SWH Architecture Documentation.* Available at: <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/architecture/metadata.html> (Accessed: 9 April 2025).

¹⁸ **B2SHARE.** (n.d.) *EUDAT Community.* Available at: <https://B2SHARE.testbed.pid.gwdg.de/communities/EUDAT> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

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access. This allows the community to know that the data exists, even if access is restricted.

If some LUMEN research data are linked to each other or to other research data that have a DOI, they will include the relevant DOI in the metadata.

Use of open, free and universal access protocols who supports authentication and authorisation

For Zenodo and B2SHARE it is possible to connect to the interface using SSO such as ORCID.

Internal LUMEN policy:
 Create an ORCID if not already done
 Anonymise personal information before sharing
 Publish under an open licence

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data format

When shared, research data produced by LUMEN will be in open format such as CSV, JSON, XML, TXT or RDF¹⁹.

Use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies

Many project members have extensive experience with EU and EOSC-related projects, enabling them to utilise the appropriate vocabulary and ensure that all references are seamlessly integrated into the global ecosystem. The accompanying metadata will be as comprehensive as possible in line with EOSC vocabularies²⁰ and the European Commission's best practices.

Extensive description of metadata

LUMEN data will incorporate precise references to external datasets through accurate citations, drawing on the consortium's long-standing involvement in similar EU projects to establish robust connections within the EOSC ecosystem and related initiatives.

¹⁹ DANS. (n.d.) *File Formats*. Available at: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

²⁰ EOSC Future. (n.d.) *EOSC Future Glossary*. Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Future+Glossary> (Accessed: 8 April 2025).

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Guidelines from organisations such as the DDI alliance²¹ and TEI Consortium²² will be applied to LUMEN research data.

Versioning system

With Zenodo, B2SHARE and Software Heritage it is possible to track the versioning of deposited research data.

Internal LUMEN policy:
 Use of open formats
 Use standardised vocabularies and ontologies - if not standardised, provide mappings
 Provide links to related datasets

2.4. Increase data re-use

Documentation

Comprehensive documentation, including methodologies and codebooks, will be provided where necessary to facilitate the reuse of shared data. Data essential for reproducing the results of the project will be deposited in public repositories and made available under standard reuse licences in accordance with the obligations of the grant agreement. The project is also committed to publishing research results in Open Access and Diamond Access journals.

Usage example

Where possible, an example of use will be linked to the data shared on public repositories so that future users/readers can repeat the process. In addition, it is envisaged to propose a list of potential contexts in which the data could be reused.

Data provenance

Data provenance will be carefully documented through comprehensive metadata, and a data quality assurance process will be implemented where appropriate. While the details of this process have not yet been finalised, intellectual property rights will be carefully considered in WP7 to ensure that the different data types are managed appropriately.

Internal LUMEN policy:
 Provide documentation and usage example linked to the datasets shared
 Clarify data provenance

²¹ **DDI Alliance.** (n.d.) *DDI Alliance*. Available at: <https://ddialliance.org/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

²² **TEI Consortium.** (n.d.) Available at: <https://tei-c.org/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025).

D1.2 DMP and Policies

3. Allocation of resources

The expected volume of research data is modest:

- Text documents = 1 GB
- Source code = 5 GB
- Audio/video recordings = 30 GB
- Experimental data = 5 GB
- Catalogues & metadata = 2 GB
- Indexing data = 50 GB
- Statistics & metrics = 5 GB

Estimated total with margin: ~100 GB

3.1 Data management budget

Delivering data that is as FAIR as possible is an integral part of the project, and as such no separate step or budget has been allocated specifically to achieve FAIR data. However, additional time will be required to curate and share the data. Project members can declare this task as time spent on the project.

In the case of long-term storage of LUMEN data, this could represent an additional cost. At the end of the project, a selection of research data and code may be published and safely preserved in a CoreTrustSeal²³ certified trustworthy data repository with transparent data security processes in place.

3.2 Responsibilities

In the context of LUMEN, the data management responsibilities are organised as follows:

- **The task and WP Leaders** are responsible to provide usage examples and documentation to reuse data. They are also responsible for converting their data in format compatible with the FAIR principles²⁴ and to provide links to related data.
- **The WP8 leaders** are responsible for depositing deliverables and workshop outputs on Zenodo.
- The **Technical Coordinator** is responsible for ensuring that research data managed within the project is deposited in trusted repositories such as B2SHARE or Software Heritage, in accordance with FAIR principles and LUMEN's federated data mesh architecture. This includes supervising the technical compliance of formats, metadata, and exposure protocols, and ensuring interoperability with EOSC-aligned services.

²³ CoreTrustSeal Requirements2023-2025_v01.00 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051011> Still R16

²⁴ **DANS**. (n.d.) *File Formats*. Available at: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/> (Accessed: 18 April 2025)

D1.2 DMP and Policies

- **The PCO** is responsible for overseeing the overall data management within the LUMEN project and for evaluating the implementation of the DMP²⁵. PCO shall provide guidance on the DMP implementation.

A detailed description of DMP responsibilities can be found in Appendix B.

3.3 Planning

Reviews and updates of this DMP are planned for months 20 and 36, in line with the LUMEN management and progress reports.

Figure 3 - Planning of LUMEN DMP updates

²⁵ See Appendix B

D1.2 DMP and Policies

4. Data security

4.1 Keeping the data safe

During the project, the research data is stored in the LUMEN Google Shared Drive, with folders per WP. This allows for file sharing across partners and the tracking of revisions.

Access to the LUMEN Shared Drive is managed by the PCO. Google's network is protected from external attacks. Data belonging to G Suite customers is stored at rest in two types of systems: disks and backup media. Google also stores data on offline backup media to help ensure recovery from any catastrophic error or natural disaster at one of their data centres. G Suite offers a data loss prevention policy to protect sensitive information within Google Drive. With respect to data protection, Google is committed to complying with the GDPR for G Suite²⁶.

To ensure that LUMEN data is not lost, the PCO is expected to perform internal backups every three months. The PCO is responsible for downloading the LUMEN Gdrive on M6, M9, M12, M15, M18, M21, M24, M27, M30, M33 and M36 to prevent the loss of all project data in the event of a system failure.

4.2 Protecting sensitive data

In the context of LUMEN, at this stage, when it comes to sensitive data, only personnel data are considered. In the project scope, no other types of sensitive data are included. A GDPR checklist is provided in Appendix C²⁷ of this DMP. It contains essential questions and steps to be taken when collecting personal data. In particular, this includes providing an informed consent document²⁸ to respondents and adding a privacy policy to the LUMEN website.

4.2.1 Collecting personal data to manage the project

The LUMEN GDrive contains a list of contacts with names, surnames, affiliations, and email addresses of its members. This list is stored in an Excel file on GDrive and is only accessible to project members. The data was voluntarily provided by the members themselves, ensuring transparency and fairness in accordance with GDPR.

²⁶ https://cloud.google.com/security/infrastructure/design/resources/google_infrastructure_whitepaper_fa.pdf and <https://cloud.google.com/security/compliance/gdpr/>

²⁷ See Appendix C

²⁸ See Appendix D

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The collected data is used exclusively for project-related communications and is not processed beyond this scope, complying with GDPR's requirement that data be collected for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes. Access to the file is strictly restricted to project members, preventing unauthorised access and ensuring data security.

Members have the right to access, rectify, or request the removal of their personal data at any time, and they can withdraw their consent to be part of the mailing list. The mailing list is maintained only for the duration of the project and will be deleted upon its conclusion unless a justified reason for retention exists, ensuring compliance with GDPR's principle of storage limitation.

The information contained in the contact list will not be shared with third parties and will only be used within the project, ensuring confidentiality and compliance with the principle of data minimisation. They will be deleted after the end of the project. By following these principles, the project ensures full compliance with GDPR and protects the privacy and rights of all members.

4.2.2 Mailing list

The use of mailing lists avoids the sharing of email addresses of project members. In the context of LUMEN, 15 mailing lists have been created²⁹. They will be deleted after the end of the project.

4.2.3 Collecting personal data for research

In the context of LUMEN, interviews will be conducted in order to better understand user needs and to develop ontologies.

When collecting data for and from interviews, this data will be stored in external storage (not in the GDrive). Once anonymised, they will be added to the GDrive and in a public repository. Participants will be given an informed consent form to sign before any information is shared³⁰.

4.2.4 Data privacy and LUMEN website

LUMEN reaches out to many organisations, individuals, and other projects, and organises interviews, workshops, and other activities, involving people from within and outside the project.

LUMEN has a privacy policy and terms of use statement for the project website, which addresses personal data (processing, data subject's rights, opt-out, cookies

²⁹ See Appendix B - Landel, S., Dumouchel, S., Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Foumany, L., Homo, J., De Paoli, S., & De Santis, L. (2025). LUMEN Deliverable 1.1 Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15082813>

³⁰ See Appendix D: informed consent template

D1.2 DMP and Policies

used on the website and in social media, etc.). The detailed privacy policy can be found on the LUMEN website³¹.

MWS is the data controller regarding all personal data processing carried out through the website, while all project partners have been identified as data processors for GDPR purposes and therefore allowed to access personal data provided via the website managed by MWS.

The LUMEN website will be kept online until the end of 2032 to support the sustainability of the project outputs.

MWS manages this website on behalf of the LUMEN consortium and is responsible for processing users' personal data in accordance with the GDPR and German data protection laws. Personal data collected includes contact data and usage statistics are processed for purposes of communication and impact monitoring. Legal bases for data processing include user consent, contractual necessity, and legitimate interests, with special rules for employee data and profiling. The site uses cookies for analytics through Matomo, with user consent required; users can revoke consent or object to data use. Contact data is collected through a Mailchimp plugin for the project's external mailing list. The mailing list itself is set up GDPR compliant, users must register through a double opt-in process. Subscribers can revoke their subscription to the mailing list at any time.

³¹ **LUMEN Project.** (n.d.) *Legal Notice & Privacy Policy.* Available at: <https://lumenproject.eu/privacy-policy/> (Accessed: 23 May 2025).

D1.2 DMP and Policies

5. Ethics

5.1 Sensitive data

The project will only process a minimal amount of personal data, including people's first names, surnames, email addresses, job titles and professional affiliations. It will not process any medical, financial or cyber security information. Where sensitive data is processed, an anonymization process is in place and an informed consent template is available for immediate use.

5.2 Intellectual Property Rights

In terms of intellectual property rights, the project involves creative contributions from the consortium members, which include both profit and non-profit organisations. Funding is provided by public sources (the European Commission), and it is expected that developments resulting from this public funding will be openly shared. However, open sharing does not mean that intellectual property is forfeited; all contributions will be accompanied by appropriate authorship and proper acknowledgement will be required whenever results are reused, cited or interpreted.

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Appendix A: list of sensitive data

Generic example of sensitive data:

Personally Identifiable Information (PII): Name, address, phone number, email, Social Security number, etc.

Sensitive PII: Information such as financial data, medical records, or personal identifiers (e.g., biometric data, religious beliefs, or sexual orientation).

Bank account numbers, credit card details, or other information related to someone's financial status.

Medical records, diagnoses, treatments, or any health-related information protected under regulations like HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act) in the U.S.

Trade secrets, intellectual property, proprietary information, or any internal business strategy or operational plans.

National security data, intelligence reports, military plans, or diplomatic communications.

Data protected by legal privilege, ongoing legal proceedings, or confidential agreements.

Passwords, encryption keys, access credentials, and anything related to the security of systems or data.

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Appendix B: DMP responsibilities - based on LUMEN internal policy

Order	Responsible	Actions	Additional actions / Information
1	PCO	Sharing good practices	DMP to be added on Zenodo
2	All project members	Create ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/
3	Task and WP leaders	Make sure that the vocabulary used is aligned with EOSC and EC vocabularies	https://eoscpilot.eu/eosc-glossary https://zenodo.org/records/4472643
4	Task and WP leaders	Whenever possible, use footnotes with DOIs to link citations	
5	Task and WP leaders	Provide files in open format such as CSV, JSON, XML, RDF	https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats
6	Task and WP leaders	Include useful disciplinary notation and terminology	https://ddialliance.org/introduction-to-ddi
7	Task and WP leaders	Indicate terms of use clearly	
8	Task and WP leaders	Describe methods of data collection and file structures	https://ddialliance.org/introduction-to-ddi
9	Task and WP leaders	Reference articles and include ORCID IDs of all data contributors	

D1.2 DMP and Policies

Order	Responsible	Actions	Additional actions / Information
10	Task and WP leaders	Provide example of use	
11	Task and WP leaders	Provide methodologies and guidelines to use the datasets	
12	Task and WP leaders	Anonymise sensitive information before sharing	See appendices A, C & D
13	Task and WP leaders	Select an open licence	see section 2.2
14	Task and WP leaders	Transmit info to WP8 and Technical coordinator	
15	WP8 Leaders	Deposit LUMEN research data on Zenodo	- Complete as much metadata fields as possible - add keywords: LUMEN, EOSC
16	Technical coordinator	Deposit LUMEN research data on B2SHARE or Software Heritage	- Complete as much metadata fields as possible - add keywords: LUMEN, EOSC

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Appendix C: checklist to identify personal data and identify concrete actions

#	Checklist Item	Required Actions
1	Identification of the data collected	When identifying personal data: GDPR applies.
2	Check the need for data	Apply the data minimisation principle - collect only what you need.
3	Check data content	If it involves data such as health, religion, political opinions or ethnicity, apply stricter safeguards - obtain explicit consent or rely on other valid legal grounds.
4	Obtain explicit consent for data from targeted individuals	Provide an informed consent form (appendix D) for people to sign before their information is collected. This document also includes information about how the information collected will be stored and shared.
5	Provision of privacy notices to data subjects	The notice should be concise, transparent and understandable, explaining the purposes, legal basis, retention, etc.
6	Check data accuracy	Implement procedures to ensure data accuracy and to correct or delete inaccurate data.
7	Define long-term data retention	Establish and document a retention schedule and ensure secure deletion of data when no longer required.
8	Check security measures to protect the data	Check if the folder / repository is public, if yes, move the data in a private one.
9	Check if data subjects exercise their rights (access, rectification, erasure, restriction, portability, objection)	Procedure to be explained in the informed consent document.

Appendix D: information consent form template

This document is inspired by the WP3 template and should be updated according to the team's work.

Informed Consent for Participation in an Interview

Project title: LUMEN - Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network

Principal Investigator: [Insert name, affiliation, and contact details]

Researcher Conducting Interviews: [Insert name, affiliation, and contact details]

Introduction

Thank you for considering participation in this research interview. Please read the following information carefully. This consent form, together with the accompanying research information sheet (which you should have received separately), explains the purpose, procedures, risks, benefits, and your rights as a participant.

Your participation is entirely voluntary. Please take your time to consider the information provided and do not hesitate to ask any questions before agreeing to take part.

1. What is the research about?

The purpose of this research is to [briefly explain the objectives of the study].

2. Do I have to take part?

This form has been written to help you decide if you would like to take part. It is up to you and you alone whether you wish to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason and without penalty.

3. What will I be required to do?

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to take part in an interview lasting approximately [insert duration]. The interview will cover topics related to [insert general topics] and may be audio-recorded with your permission. The recording will be used solely for research purposes and subsequently transcribed.

4. How will you handle my data?

Your data will be stored in a pseudonymised form and will only be accessible to researchers from [insert organisation collecting the data]. This means that a key stored separately will link your research data to your real identity.

Your data will be stored in [insert organisation collecting the data] secure research drive, with data anonymized at the earliest opportunity. Your responses are treated in the strictest confidence - it will be impossible to identify individuals within a dataset when any of the research is disseminated (e.g., in publications/presentations). [insert organisation collecting the data] acts as Data Controller [insert email address of organisational data controller].

The [interview, registry, etc.] will be [audio/video/etc.] recorded, and later [transcribed, analysed, listed]. The analysis may also be conducted with software located in the cloud, always in a fully GDPR compliant manner. Should you have questions about the research please contact [organisation collecting the data with email address].

5. Retention of research data

Researchers are obliged to retain research data for up to 10 years' post-publication, however your anonymised research data may be retained indefinitely (e.g., so that researchers engage in open practice and other researchers can access their data to confirm the conclusions of published work). Consistent with our data retention policy, researchers retain consent forms for as long as we continue to hold information about a data subject and for 10 years for published research (including Research Degree thesis).

Should the dataset be deemed of scientific interest, it could be deposited after the research is published in the Open Access repository Zenodo, with data fully anonymised.

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6. Consent statement

The data collected during this interview may be used in academic publications, presentations, or reports. In all cases, your identity will remain confidential, and all reported data will be aggregated.

[insert organisation collecting the data] attaches high priority to the ethical conduct of research. Please consider the following before indicating your consent on this form. Indicating your consent confirms that you are willing to participate in the research, however, indicating consent does not commit you to anything you do not wish to do and you are free to withdraw your participation at any time. You are indicating consent under the following assumptions:

- I understand the contents of the participant information sheet and consent form.
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the research and have had them answered satisfactorily.
- I understand that my participation is entirely voluntary and that I can withdraw from the research (parts of the project or the entire project) at any time without penalty and without having to provide an explanation.
- I understand who has access to my data and how it will be handled at all stages of the research project.

PLEASE INITIAL BOX:	Yes, I do consent	No, I do not consent
I consent to take part in this study conducted by [insert organisation collecting the data] who intend to use my data for the design of GoTriple and for the conduction of the LUMEN project.		

I confirm that I am willing to take part in this research:

PRINT NAME (for paper-based forms): [XXXXX]

SIGNATURE (for paper-based forms):

[XXXXX]

DATE: [XXXXX]

D1.2 DMP and Policies

You can find our procedure for complaints (regarding research projects) and our privacy notice and legal basis for processing research data at:
<https://lumenproject.eu/privacy-policy/>

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